

A brief estimation of deaths in Germany caused by short-term adverse reactions to SARS-CoV-2 vaccines

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Key words: severe adverse event; autopsy; all-cause mortality

1 Abstract

2 Background: While the efficacy of the newly developed mRNA and vector vaccines against SARS-CoV-
3 2 have been widely advertised, their harm-to-benefit ratio still remains widely ignored. Though, reports
4 of possible side effects are piling up. The most severe of those side effects is a sudden and unexpected
5 death, with liability issues inducing strong incentives to communicate potentially associated mortalities
6 always aligned with the particular motives and interests. Accordingly, reliable estimates of how many
7 deaths might have been actually caused by the vaccination are still missing up to date, to the best of our
8 knowledge, in Germany at least. (2) Methods: Here, we fill this void and provide such an estimate for
9 Germany during the course of 2021. Thereto, the number of deaths reported by the Paul-Ehrlich-Institut
10 to have occurred within the group of people suspectedly struck by a vaccine-induced adverse event is
11 scaled by the factor of under-reporting, based on health insurance reports, and finally corrected by known
12 all-cause mortality. (3) Results: Our point estimate for the year 2021 alone reaches a total of 16,817 (short-
13 term) deaths caused by SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. Taking independent autopsy reports into account, the
14 estimate of 11,194 deaths is the lower bound. (4) Conclusions: This report may serve as a pivot for further
15 investigations in this matter.

16 Graphical abstract

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1. Introduction

In a recent study [1], the authors calculated a harm-to-benefit ratio of mRNA vaccines, delivered to young people in the United States, by analysing data from the ‘Centers for Disease Control and Prevention’ (CDC). For the vaccinated cohort, they documented an absolute reduction in the risk of CoViD-19 hospitalisation of no more than 0.002-0.003% compared to the unvaccinated cohort. In other words, over 30,000 subjects had to be vaccinated to prevent a single case of CoViD-19 hospitalisation. Concomitantly, the authors calculated that 18.5 cases of *severe* adverse events (SAE), which in part resulted in hospitalisation, were accompanied by each a case of prevented CoViD-19 hospitalisation. Approximately 8%-25% of the SAE resulted in myopericarditis, a life-threatening condition. Their harm-to-benefit ratio of 18.5 well matches [2] who analysed just a specific selection of *serious* AE in the original clinical trial data (ratios above 1 in all vaccines), as well as our own findings [3] in the earliest published data of some pivotal clinical trials of SARS-CoV-2 (mRNA or vector) vaccines: ratios between 0.6 and 25 for *severe* AE at least, with 3.6 for explicitly *serious* AE conditions in one mRNA vaccine [4]. Further papers, e.g. [5], likewise document a significant risk of myopericarditis inflicted by mRNA and vector vaccines. As a note, more than 75% of the CDC-documented SAE resulted in other conditions requiring hospitalisation, with myopericarditis not being the only life-threatening AE condition induced by SARS-CoV-2 vaccination.

Naturally, some of the life-threatening SAE result in death. In Germany, AE suspectedly induced by vaccines are registered on a ‘to be notified’ basis (which applies to the PEI requesting German physicians based on their assessment), and have been regularly reported by the Paul-Ehrlich-Institut (PEI), during 2021 at least. In that year—or, more exactly, from the beginning of the vaccine campaign on 27/12/2020 until the end of June 2022—the PEI reported 3,023 deaths suspected to be due to SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. As a side note, this number is basically a *conditional* death count, namely, within the group of people suspected to show an AE, which is a fatality selection widely different from the commonly used, simple *unconditional* (i.e. *all-cause*, see further below) death count. It has been concluded from autopsies [6] that up to 80% [7] of suspectedly vaccine-related deaths were indeed caused by SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. It is also well documented in general [8] and across countries [9, 10, 11, 12] that AE registration procedures suffer from dramatic under-registration, with well beyond 90% of drug-related AE not being registered by authorities [13, p. 30].

In view of the uncertainties mentioned, this paper aims to report a reliably estimated number of deaths, which were actually *caused* by vaccines against SARS-CoV-2 infection, in Germany over the year 2021. Data basis and starting point are (i) the suspected AE counts registered in the ‘to be notified’ data base run by the PEI, and (ii) the AE fractions of the sub-counts of SAE and deaths, respectively. We then scale the PEI number of suspected AE, while retaining the SAE and death fractions, by means of the number of medical treatments due to AE as reported by the German-wide health insurance accountant of medical treatments, the ‘Kassenärztliche Bundesvereinigung’ (KBV) [14], and by one of the German health insurance companies (‘BKK ProVita’) [15, 16], which had independently analysed treatment data of a sub-population. We further estimate the number of expected all-cause deaths within the AE whole sub-group of Germans, and contrast the suspected versus the expected deaths [17], the excess being our point estimate of deaths cause by vaccination. Autopsy data [6, 7, 18, 19] allow us to eventually estimate a lower boundary to the number of deaths actually caused by SARS-CoV-2 vaccines.

2. Methods and results: data handling and calculations

This section provides a detailed explanation of the Graphical Abstract above, with the item numbers ‘X)’ corresponding to the paragraphs following next.

1) First, we calculate both the SAE and the death fraction of the number of AE suspected to be due to SARS-CoV-2 vaccines, according to the latest two associated safety reports of the PEI [20, 21]. While the *absolute* AE, SAE, and death numbers are under-estimated in the PEI reports [13, p. 30], the *fractions* therein can well be considered characteristic parameters of the German SARS-CoV-2 vaccination

66 campaign. From the beginning of the campaign on December 27th, 2020 until June 30th, 2022, 323,684
67 suspected cases of subjects suffering an AE were counted, 43,911 cases of suspected SAE, and 3,023 people
68 suspected to have died from vaccination [21]. Adopting the one-year-after report [20] as a second data
69 source (244,576 AE, 29,786 SAE, and 2,255 deaths), we calculate a mean SAE fraction of 12.9% and a
70 mean death fraction of 0.9% within the group of people having suspectedly suffered an AE.

71 **2) Second**, the issue of AE under-reporting by the PEI can be resolved using data provided by the
72 KBV: In their response [14] to a request by a Member of Parliament (‘Bundestag’), the KBV acting as the
73 public health insurance accountant reported close to 2.5 million subjects who had consulted a physician
74 in 2021 due to a vaccine-related AE. The KBV reporting reflects about 90% of German physicians who
75 claimed compensation for their treatments referring to the ICD code U12.9 (‘International Statistical
76 Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems’; unspecified adverse reactions associated with the
77 inoculation by COVID-19 vaccines) for over 90% of the AE cases. These are 10.2 times more AE cases than
78 reported by the PEI. This KBV-to-PEI ratio is in line with the wide-spread, practically general degree of
79 under-reporting [8] on voluntary or ‘to be notified’ bases (which, e.g., applies to the PEI requesting German
80 physicians based on their assessment), as it is with a published comparison [9, 11, 12] of registration rates
81 across European countries. Moreover, the KBV treatment numbers are in almost perfect alignment with
82 n AE due to SARS-CoV-2 vaccination during the year 2021, we can calculate, by multiplication with
83 the corresponding PEI-based fractions, the number of persons having suspectedly suffered a *severe* AE
84 (320,891) or even died (22,388).

85 **4) Fourth**, we subtract from the number of people, who have suspectedly died after receiving the
86 vaccination in the year 2021 (22,388) the number of persons who were to be expected to die within that
87 year and within the ‘PEI-monitored’ time window after vaccination, all based on the known annual *all-*
88 *cause* mortality [22, 23]. This method of calculating *excess* mortality under any side condition has been
89 worked out recently [17]. To find how many persons must have died due to all causes anyway (within
90 the specific group of interest, here, those with a suspected AE), three further pieces of information are
91 required: (i) the annual all-cause mortality rates of all age cohorts represented within those vaccinated;
92 (ii) the time span after injection during which the PEI ‘accepts’ a fatality of a suspected AE case to be
93 possibly due to the vaccine, 50 days [20, p. 9] (later [21]: data given for 30 days); and (iii) the vaccination
94 quota of each age cohort. The number of people *expected* to die for any reason (all-cause mortality) within
95 a defined time span can be computed by

$$\begin{aligned} n_{T,ac} &= n_{pop} \cdot r_{ann} \cdot T \\ &= n_{pop} \cdot (a_{young} \cdot r_{young} + a_{old} \cdot r_{old}) \cdot T \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

96 with n_{pop} being the referenced number of persons constituting the specific sub-population of interest, r_{ann}
97 the annual all-cause death rate, and T a fraction of time, which would be 1 for a whole year. For higher
98 accuracy, the population can be divided into age cohorts—e.g. particularly *older* (≥ 60 years of age) and
99 *younger* (< 60 years)—with their respective cohort-specific relative fractions (a_{young} and a_{old}) of n_{pop} and
100 death rates ($r_{young} = 0.0019$ and $r_{old} = 0.041$), which were adopted from [17]. These rates were computed
101 by dividing the number of people within these age groups [22] by the corresponding number of reported
102 deaths [23].

103 By the end of 2021, about 59.5 million (of total 83.4 million) Germans had been “fully” vaccinated [20].
104 Neglecting therein, due to both their fraction and their annual death rates being small, the 2.4 million
105 youngsters below 18 years of age, we can calculate the number $n_{50d,ac}$ of all-cause deaths to be expected
106 within the 50 days after the ‘date of injection’:

$$\begin{aligned} n_{50d,ac} &= \frac{50}{365} \cdot 2,487,526 \cdot \\ &\quad \left(\frac{36.0}{59.5 - 2.4} \cdot 0.0019 + \frac{21.1}{59.5 - 2.4} \cdot 0.041 \right) \\ &= 5,571 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

107 Because any suspected death by vaccination counted by the PEI is from the sub-population of suspected
 108 AE (count n_{AE}), $n_{pop} = n_{AE} = 2,487,526$ holds for our estimation of expected deaths, with the PEI value
 109 of $n_{AE} = 244,576$ simply being replaced (upscaled) by the KBV number of all those treated under ICD
 110 code U12.9. The difference of $16,817 = 22,388 - 5,571$ between estimated suspected deaths (PEI-to-KBV-
 111 upscaled n_{AE} just like for the AE, with then simply multiplying n_{AE} by the PEI-provided death fraction
 112 of n_{AE} ; result: 22,388) and expected deaths (5,571) represents the *excess* deaths that are thought to be
 113 caused by the vaccine itself. In other words, according to our estimation, 75% of suspected deaths were
 114 due to unexpected cause.

115 **5) Fifth**, other sources allow to estimate a lower bound of our point estimate of 16,817 vaccine-induced
 116 short-term fatalities. The numbers of AE, SAE, and deaths counted by the PEI are labelled “suspected”.
 117 This label is due to the PEI not checking for specific causes of the fatal health issues, which is, however,
 118 possible through autopsies. Indeed, there are very few, albeit unambiguous histo-chemical autopsy data
 119 that verify a direct link between SARS-CoV-2 vaccination and death. Autopsy reports from a German
 120 team of pathologists document a range from originally at least 33% [6] to, given more recently, 80% [7]
 121 for the vaccination being the cause of death in suspected cases. While this original/initial value of 33%
 122 had well matched the range 30-40% reported [18] already three months earlier by a another German
 123 team of pathologists, the more recent value [7] of 80% matches the 75% based on our excess-to-all-cause
 124 estimation. Note the critical remarks [24] having been made on this latter work [7] to possibly contain
 125 some methodical issues. A more recently published value of the second team dropped to 5 out of 35 [19],
 126 i.e. just 14%. However, they had then searched for evidence of only and exactly one conventional fatal
 127 mechanism, namely, myocarditis. Due to their extremely limiting search focus, we omit their results in a
 128 preliminary estimation of a percentage of vaccination being causative among suspected deaths; as a start,
 129 we estimate this factor from preliminary autopsy data as the arithmetic mean of 33% [25], 35% (mean
 130 of 30-40%) [18], and 80% [7], i.e. about 50%. With this, we can give an estimate of the lower bound of
 131 vaccine-induced short-term fatalities, namely, half of the 22,388 suspected deaths, i.e. 11,194.

132 3. Discussion

133 Eventually, we have arrived at what we initially aimed for: The 2,255 suspected deaths from vaccination,
 134 officially reported by the PEI [20, 21], were upscaled to 22,388 due to under-reporting by the PEI as
 135 indicated by the KBV and BKK numbers of accounted U12.9 treatments by physicians [14, 15, 16] in
 136 relation to suspected AE being counted by the PEI, and corrected by roughly 25% to 16,817 due to the
 137 expected all-cause mortality [17]. As a comparison, 16,817 excess deaths due to SARS-CoV-2 vaccination
 138 during 2021 correspond to two thirds of the excess deaths of the most severe influenza epidemics in Germany
 139 between 2000 and 2019, namely 25,100 in the season 2017/18 according to the RKI [29]. Boiled down
 140 to a single small number, the *excess mortality rate* σ_{vacc} of the German 2021 SARS-CoV-2 vaccination
 141 campaign, defined as the ratio between observed (here: ‘suspected’ by physicians) and expected mortality
 142 ($22,388/5,571$), equals $\sigma_{vacc} = 4$. That is, the probability of dying from any cause within the vaccinated
 143 population, *and if therein being suspectedly struck by an AE*, is quadrupled in comparison to the risk of
 144 dying due to any cause within the overall population. A synopsis of all input and output (estimated)
 145 numbers is given in Table 1.

146 3.1. A comparison with non-German reports and pivotal clinical trial data

147 Our basic assumption is that the count (244,576) of AE registered (practically only by physicians) in the
 148 PEI-run database in 2021 [20] divided by the count (2,487,526) of patients AE-treated (ICD code U12.9:
 149 well over 90% of all treatments) by German physicians (as compensated by public health insurance and
 150 registered by KBV, covering roughly 90% of treatments in Germany) is an estimate (0.0983) of the factor
 151 of under-reporting generally observable [8, 13] in AE registration databases, and particularly in Germany
 152 during the ‘SARS-CoV-2 era’. A comparison [9, fig. 1],[11, fig. 1] of German with Luxembourgian and

Table 1: Counts n_{AE} of suspected *adverse events* (AE), n_{SAE} of suspected *severe adverse events* (SAE), and n_{Xd} ($X = 30, 50$; ‘ d ’ means ‘days of monitoring (by PEI)’) of suspected *deaths* in Germany due to SARS-CoV-2 (mRNA or vector) vaccination as documented by the PEI [20] during 2021 (more exactly, for the campaign 27/12/2020-31/12/2021), with computed n_{SAE} and n_{Xd} *fractions of* n_{AE} , as well as *excess mortality ratio(s)* $\sigma_{Xd,vac}$ of SARS-CoV-2 vaccination; in mid 2022, the PEI reported [21] a n_{30d} one-time count. **Counts** and the two n_{AE} **fractions derived therefrom** are printed in **bold font**, further calculated numbers otherwise. Each n_{AE} fraction value is the arithmetic mean of the values calculated from the two counts, until end of 2021 and mid 2022, respectively. — All $n_{Xd,ac}$ values have been calculated using Eq. (1) with varied $n_{pop} = n_{AE}$ and T values, i.e. correspondingly replacing 2,487,526 and $\frac{50}{365}$ in Eq. (3), while r_{ann} being a constant (value 0.01635 in parentheses of Eq. (3)). — The number $n_{Xd,exc} = n_{Xd} - n_{Xd,ac}$ of *suspected deaths in excess of expected all-cause deaths* is our final estimate of the number of *deaths caused by vaccination*. — The vaccine-induced *excess mortality ratio* $\sigma_{Xd,vac} = \frac{n_{Xd}}{n_{Xd,ac}}$ quantifies the increased, in relation to regular all-cause mortality, probability to die, *given* being struck by an AE. — Among 83.4 million Germans, until 31/12/2021, about 59.5 million persons had been vaccinated twice at least (vaccination quotas: [26, Abb. 17]; age cohort strengths: [22]), with about 148.8 million doses [20] inoculated, and until 30/06/2022, 63.6 million persons [27, Abb. 19],[22], with 182.7 million doses [21]. — See text for a lower $n_{50d,exc}$ bound estimated from autopsy data.

data sources PEI ₂₀₂₁ [20]		... PEI _{mid2022} [21]		n_{AE} fraction	... KBV ₂₀₂₁ [14]	
n_{AE}		244,576		323,684			2,487,526	
n_{SAE}		29,786		43,911		0.129 (12.9%)	320,891	
n_{50d}	$[n_{30d}]$	2,255	[1,391]	3,023	[1,865]	0.009 (0.9%)	22,388	[13,812]
$n_{50d,ac}$	$[n_{30d,ac}]$	548	[329]	725	[435]		5,571	[3,343]
$n_{50d,exc}$	$[n_{30d,exc}]$	1,707	[1,062]	2,298	[1,430]		16,817	[10,469]
$\sigma_{50d,vac}$	$[\sigma_{30d,vac}]$	4.1	[4.2]	4.2	[4.3]		4.0	[4.1]

153 Estonian AE registration rates (them second to the ‘winner’ Netherlands) reveals almost identical ratios
154 of 0.092. Thus, our assumption of a 10.2-fold ($= \frac{1}{0.0983}$) under-reporting of AE in Germany stands on
155 solid grounds. Accordingly, we can treat the count of physician-suspected and -acknowledged, and thus
156 KBV-registered AE patients to be an estimate much closer to the actual number of AE (even more, a
157 sound count of *persons* definitely struck) than the (suspected) AE count given by the PEI.

158 A current study has estimated the number of deaths caused by SARS-CoV-2 vaccines in the USA to be
159 between 217,330 and 332,608 [30]. These authors assumed that 51% of the US population (331.5 million)
160 had been vaccinated, and the fraction of people that had suffered a SAE within the group of people showing
161 a suspected AE was 13%, with the latter number perfectly matching the fraction of 12.9% reported by the
162 German PEI. In absolute numbers, this US study thus estimated that two million US citizens would have
163 been suspected to suffer a SAE, which corresponds to a SAE frequency ν_{SAE} within the US population of
164 118 in 10,000 persons ($\nu_{SAE} = \frac{2}{0.51 \cdot 331.5} \cdot 10,000 \approx 118$). Accordingly, the excess mortality rate within the
165 group of US citizens suspected to show an AE would be more than nine times higher than the US-common
166 all-cause mortality, compared to the quadrupled rate (see above) in Germany. Acknowledging the common
167 fact of under-reporting [8], and the different registration processes of suspected AE data, as well as, mainly,
168 vaccines being somehow differently confected for administration to US recipients than to Germans, the
169 numbers from [30] well fit our present calculations.

170 We have just estimated the frequency of SAE in the US population as a response to being vaccinated
171 with a SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. What is now the corresponding value in Germany due to our scaling from
172 PEI to KBV data, as summarised in Table 1? The answer is given in Table 2, along with a cross-check
173 by the frequency values that can be calculated from the published data on the pivotal clinical trials of
174 five SARS-CoV-2 (mRNA and vector) vaccines [4, 31, 32, 33, 34]. The result is again surpassing our
175 KBV-based claim: A value of $\nu_{SAE} = 119$ SAE per 10,000 persons should have been expected in Germany

176 from the pivotal trial data (which is extremely close to the value 118 observed in the USA), whereas our
 177 PEI-scaling by KBV data yields $\nu_{SAE} = 54$ SAE per 10,000 persons in Germany. Hence, our SAE point
 178 estimate is well conservative, which renders our estimate of 16,817 deaths caused by vaccination likewise
 179 conservative. We do not comment here on the corresponding SAE frequencies in the pivotal trials’ control
 180 groups. These may well be worth further in-depth investigations, but such would go beyond the scope of
 181 this paper. That the frequency $\nu_{serAESI}$ of *serious AE of special interest (serAESI)* found by Fraiman et al.
 182 [2] in the pivotal trial data is a factor of ten lower than in the SAE category of the same data (first
 183 two data rows in Table 2) is not surprising at all, as *serAESI* are first of all the close-to-life-threatening
 184 sub-category of SAE (*‘serious’* even within *‘severe’*), and a specific sub-selection of specific events within
‘serious’ AE in addition.

Table 2: Fractions (frequencies) ν_{SAE} of the number of SAE (recall: *‘severe’*) per 10,000 subjects *vaccinated* (and in the *control* groups) for five mRNA or vector SARS-CoV-2 vaccines, according to each the first paper published on the safety and efficacy data gathered in the pivotal clinical trial studies (phase-3; see ‘data source’). “placebos” were specified as inoculations in the *control* groups of the trials of the first three vaccines, by Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna, and Johnson&Johnson/Janssen. In the second column, the percentage fraction of administered vaccine doses is given for Germany; for BNT162b2, the frequency ν_{serAE} of category *‘serious’* AE (*serAE*) is also available from [4]; the numbers to calculate the frequencies in this table are directly taken from [3, tab. 1] (see there for details, remarks, and explanations about the studies and numbers extracted therefrom), i.e. the SAE (and *serAE*) frequencies are $\nu_{AE} = \frac{N_{SAE,vac}}{N_t}$ (and $\nu_{AE} = \frac{N_{SAE,com}}{N_t}$ for the *control* groups); the in-depth study [2] has analysed the pivotal clinical trial data of the first two vaccines with respect to the frequencies $\nu_{serAESI}$ of *‘serious’* AE *‘of special interest’* (*serAESI*); the SAE (recall: *‘severe’* AE) fraction or frequency, respectively, estimated in this study from KBV data by upscaling (compensating the under-reporting) from the SAE number counted by the PEI (details in items 1)-3) in Sec. 2) is given in the last row (Table 1: $\frac{320,891}{59,500,000} \cdot 10,000 \approx 54$).

vaccine	% in Germany [21]	data source	ν_{AE} {control}	ν_{serAE} {control}	$\nu_{serAESI}$ [2]
BNT162b2	74	[4, fig. 3, tabs. S3, S5]	111 {64}	58 {51}	10
mRNA-1273	17	[31, tabs. S8, S10]	154 {133}		15
Ad26.COV2.S	2	[32, tabs. 2, S7]	21 {10}		
Sputnik V	0	[33, tab. 2]	27 {42}		
AZD1222	7	[34]	145 {157}		
Germany-weighted means:			119 {81}	58 {51}	11
KBV		[14]	54		

185
 186 If we assume that not every German who had suspectedly been struck by an AE saw a physician for
 187 treatment, and if we further assume that the vaccine batches [35] inoculated in Germany had not been
 188 of qualities significantly different from those administered in the Netherlands, then the factor of under-
 189 reporting of suspected AE in Germany would be the ratio between Dutch and German frequencies of safety
 190 reportings [9, fig. 1],[11, fig. 1], namely, $\frac{701}{38} = 18.4$ instead of 10.2 determined as the KBV-to-PEI factor
 191 above; this factor of 18.4 would correspond perfectly to the reported median percentage of under-reporting,
 192 94% [8]. Accordingly, our point estimate of deaths in Germany caused in the short term by SARS-CoV-2
 193 vaccines in 2021 would scale up to 30,337 ($= \frac{18.4}{10.2} \cdot 16,817$), and the number of suspected SAE to 578,862,
 194 the latter number being about 1% of those Germans vaccinated until the end of 2021 (59.5 million). Note
 195 that our estimated *lower bound* of deaths by SARS-CoV-2 vaccination in the short term likewise scales
 196 with the factor of under-reporting, i.e. with 18.4 instead of 10.2, the lower bound would rise to 20,187.

4. Final words and conclusions

It is worth noting, that the KBV itself rates ICD codes as representing harmless events – because not complying with the criteria formulated for an AE ‘to be notified’ to the PEI by a physician – in an obvious attempt to attenuate their own data of 2.5 million adverse events after vaccination in the year 2021 [14]. Despite this, in the exact same document an impressive increase of vaccine-related ICD code registration by physicians is given: For the years 2016 to 2020, the number of AEs per vaccination is 0.0029, or 0.3%. In 2021, this number is 0.016 or 1.6%, a more than 5-fold increase of adverse events. The CoViD-19 vaccination campaign suggested people to get vaccinated two times or more, so the rate for a vaccine induced adverse event *per subject* increased almost 10-fold in 2021. Eventually, it has been found in a study [36] surveying employees’ days absent in response to their full vaccination (second dose) that 10.5% of them were unable to work for at least *two* days after the injection of the (mRNA) vaccine (‘BNT162b2’) that inflicted the *least* AE; it caused at least *one* day of absence in 22.7%.

It is also and again worth noting that the PEI traces suspected death cases for only 50 days after the date of injection [20, p. 9]. Then, in the mid 2022 PEI report [21], suspected deaths were also given for a shorter ‘monitoring interval’ after injection, namely, for only 30 days. Interestingly, these two counts given in [21], $n_{50d} = 3,023$ and $n_{30d} = 1,865$, perfectly reflect time-linear accumulation of suspected deaths between days 30 and 50. Therefore, the number $n_{50d,exc} = 16,817$ of *excess* deaths suspected *within 50 days* after vaccination can be seen as a reliable point estimate of the number of deaths *caused by SARS-CoV-2 vaccination within short terms* in Germany in 2021.

As a further note, the corresponding population-averaged excess mortality rate σ_{NF} specific for deaths conditional to the population (a sub-group of all Germans) of NAA-test-positive persons (the putatively ‘SARS-CoV-2 infected’; ‘NAA’ for ‘nucleic acid amplification’, including PCR-based methods; index $_{NF}$ for ‘NAA-test-positive fatality’) has been $\sigma_{NF} \approx 2.7$ for each of the whole-year periods 2020 and 2021, and $\sigma_{NF} \approx 4.3$ for the respective ‘flu seasons’ 2020/2021 and 2021/2022 [17]. Accordingly, for a German who is suspected to be struck by an AE due to SARS-CoV-2 vaccination, the quadrupling ($\sigma_{vacc} \approx 4$) of the likelihood to die is a higher increase in mortality risk than if having received a positive NAA (usually PCR) test ($\sigma_{NF} \approx 2.7$), averaged across a year and all age cohorts. As a further fact, there has not been any significantly increased mortality risk in the NAA-test-positive younger than 60 years ($\sigma_{NF} \leq 1$) [17], i.e. $\sigma_{NF} \approx 2.7$, averaged over a year, is solely due to the risk being increased beyond the common level by SARS-CoV-2 infection of those older than 60 years. In contrast, the risk to die due to vaccination is equally increased across age cohorts, if not more pronounced in the younger.

Certainly, physiological processes are induced by mRNA or vector vaccines that have immediately fatal consequences in only a sub-group of persons being particularly sensitive to these processes; accordingly, this immediate effect of vaccination vanishes as a measurable phenomenon in the population when a mass vaccination campaign ends. Observing the upcoming years and decades will be crucial to decide (if systematic sampling will be undertaken, employing sound scientific techniques like systematic autopsies), whether and how significantly SARS-CoV-2-vaccine-induced mortality shows up in the long term after the world-wide vaccination campaign in 2021 (plus 2022).

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Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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